

Significant Gene Array Analysis and Cluster-Based Machine Learning for Breast Cancer Relapse Prediction

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Abstract

Gene expression analysis plays an essential role in disease risk assessment and prediction. The use of machine learning (ML) on gene expression analysis has been of great interest, in recent years and hence, evaluation of different ML approaches will provide insight on the potential use. This study evaluates the performance of ML models when we have a domain where the number of samples is much smaller than the number of features (genes), and there is a high degree of gene-gene correlation. We have incorporated clusters of genes that showcase an effective biologically driven ML approach to uncover differentially expressed (DE) genes. In this regard, four machine learning models were evaluated: (a) random forest, (b) random forest with Gene eXpression Network Analysis (RF-2), (c) RF++, and (d) Bayesian Neural Networks (BNN) have been investigated on two breast cancer data sets obtained from Gene Omnibus Database (GSE 2034 and GSE 2990). We have incorporated the Automatic Relevance Determination prior with BNN to assess the relative importance of genes. Out of these ML methods, RF-2 showed appealing results with an average area under the receive operating characteristic curve (AUC) value of 70% and 78%, respectively, on GSE 2034 and GSE 2990. This was followed by BNN with average AUCs of 55% and 64%, respectively. Several genes including SERPINA3, ID1, RSN1, and MAD2L1 were consistently ranked within top 25 based on the mean decrease in accuracy, by at least two ML methods and are in need of further investigation.

Key Words: Bayesian Neural Network, random forest, gene networks

1. Introduction

Breast cancer is a significant public health issue, particularly for women in the USA. It is the second leading cause of cancer death in women, accounting for approximately 13% of total cancer deaths worldwide. The lifetime risk of developing breast cancer for women is estimated to be 1 in 8, and the mortality rate from breast cancer is approximately 1 in 39. In 2023, an estimated 297,790 new cases of invasive breast cancer and 55,720 new cases of non-invasive (in situ) breast cancer were diagnosed. The five-year relative survival rate for breast cancer is 90%, highlighting the importance of early detection in reducing the threat of this disease [1].

Gene expression analysis is a critical step in understanding the relationship between genotype and phenotype. Machine learning techniques, including k-nearest neighbor, support vector machines, random forests, and artificial neural networks, have been widely used in gene expression studies to improve diagnoses in healthcare and clinical applications [2], [3], [4], [5]. Bayesian networks have also been applied to gene expression data [6], but there is a need for more research to incorporate gene interaction networks into machine learning models. Nevertheless, it is generally well known that genes do not act by themselves, but rather in closely linked sets of genes or pathways that are all necessary to perform a function, known to us as “clusters”; if one gene is missing from the cluster, the intended phenotypic function cannot be performed. However, while the idea that co-expression is touched on, nothing has been introduced as of yet to determine the most important genes in these classifications. There is a lack of studies that have incorporated gene interaction networks such as those identified by the Gene eXpression Network Analysis (GXNA) into the random forest models as a hybrid approach to analyzing gene expression data.

The primary objective of this study is to evaluate the performance of the models in scenarios where the number of samples is smaller than the number of features (genes) and there is a high degree of gene-gene correlation. The study will also examine the impact of using biologically driven gene clusters in machine learning methods. The secondary objective is to use Automatic Relevance Determination (ARD) with a Bayesian neural network to identify the relative importance of genes in the network, with the validation of any identified genes performed through wet-lab analysis.

2. Methodology

2.1 Subject Data

The primary outcome variable (the dependent variable) in this study was the disease state of a subject. In this regard, we investigated on two gene expression datasets for breast cancer obtained from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) [7], a public access database maintained by the National Center for Biotechnology Information, are:

- GSE 2034: This dataset contains the gene expression data of 230 subjects, of which 144 subjects were lymph-node negative relapse-free patients, and 86 subjects were lymph-node negative patients that developed distant metastasis. All patients were female. Of the 86 subjects identified with breast cancer, ten subjects further metastasized to the brain and spinal cord through the blood or lymph system.
- GSE 2990: This dataset contains the gene expression data of 149 subjects, of which 93 subjects were lymph-node negative relapse-free patients and 56 subjects were lymph-node negative patients that developed distant metastasis. All patients were female. Of the 56 subjects identified with breast cancer, the use of gene expression grade indexing was performed to determine histologic grading of tumors was an effective method to predict recurrence.

2.2 Data Preprocessing

All gene expression data was first retrieved using a custom chip description file (CDF) from the R Bioconductor or retrieved manually from Bioconductor source files. Custom CDFs in Affymetrix GeneChips were based on the best gene clustering and genomic sequence information available at the time of chip design [7]. Affymetrix gene platforms contain a significant portion of the cluster where a subset of oligonucleotide probes in a probe set may be assigned to another gene or more than one gene. To remedy this situation the custom CDF allows for the removal of extra probes to ease interpretation of data [8]. Probe data containing 25 base-pair length oligonucleotides used to match to the RNA targets of specified genes were normalized using *germa* normalization techniques from R Bioconductor. *germa* adjusts for background intensities in Affymetrix gene data, including optical noise and non-specific binding using probe sequence information to estimate probe affinity [9]. In addition to normalization, Affy control probes were removed. A non-specific filtration of genes called *pOverA* [10] was applied to each dataset. This retains the genes which has a certain expression value “A” or above, in at least p% of the samples [10]. In this study, genes had an unlogged normalized intensity greater than 100 in at least 20% of samples. Moreover, we have selected the genes which has a coefficient variance between a minimum of 0.7 and a maximum of 10 (genes with a high variation are cut off to limit our focus on genes that do not have high variation compared to their mean). Dataset subjects were partitioned into 70%:30% training and testing subsets for model evaluations, respectively. The data analysis was performed using R (version 4.0.3) software. All tests were two-tailed and performed at a significance level of 0.05.

3. Data Analysis

3.1 Overview of Microarrays

Microarray analysis is a widely used technology in genomics and personalized medicine to study gene expression in different tissues, including breast cancer. The analysis involves hybridizing fluorescently labeled cDNA or RNA probes to a microarray slide, where specific genes are immobilized in defined spots on the slide. The fluorescence signals generated by the hybridized probes

are then quantified, providing information on the relative expression levels of thousands of genes in a single experiment. In breast cancer research, microarray analysis is commonly used to identify differentially expressed genes between normal and cancerous tissues, as well as between different subtypes of breast cancer. This information is valuable in understanding the molecular mechanisms underlying breast cancer development and progression, and can be used to develop more targeted and effective treatments. The significant analysis of microarray data involves multiple steps, including normalization, quality control, and statistical analysis. Normalization is necessary to account for technical variability in the experiment, such as differences in probe labeling and hybridization efficiency. Quality control is important to identify and exclude any samples or genes with low or inconsistent expression. After the normalization and quality control steps, statistical analysis is performed to identify differentially expressed genes.

3.2 Random Forest (RF-1)

Random Forest (RF) is a supervised machine learning technique that is often used for classification purposes. It consists of an ensemble of decision trees, each one constructed from a bootstrapped sample of observations [11]. In this analysis, disease states are considered as the observations. To reduce the correlation between trees, the best split is selected from a random subset of predictors instead of all predictors. This technique is well-suited for microarray data analysis due to its ability to handle high-dimensional data with good predictive performance and to identify the most substantial set of genes that show significant variation between disease state subjects [12]. RF is also capable of handling data with a lot of “noise” (in the case of microarrays [13], noise would be considered non-specific binding of probes) and outliers [11]. This method utilizes the concept of bootstrap aggregation, commonly known as bagging, in which the results of multiple trees are aggregated, and the random vector is generated as counts towards a target [14]. The bootstrapped sample of a specified size is drawn with replacement from the original dataset [11]. Within the training set, 1/3 of patients are left out of the model or bag to calculate an “out-of-bag” (OOB) error rate for the validity of the model. The OOB generalized error rate is used to measure the prediction error rate of decision trees for a sub-sample set used for training. For instance, in GSE 2034, OOB subjects are assigned a prediction classification based on where they end up after going through the “forest” and the OOB measures the accuracy of their classification into 1: No Relapse or 2: Relapse. The goal of this is to find the decision tree within the RF model with the lowest OOB score, or most accurate prediction [15].

3.3 Random Forest with Gene eXpression Network Analysis (GXNA) (RF-2)

GXNA is a computational algorithm introduced by Nacu et al. in 2007 [16] which uses mRNA expression and protein–protein interactions to identify functionally active gene subnetworks. Nodes are defined as genes, while edges correspond to protein–protein interactions. The method first assesses the significance of differential gene expression for every node. Substantial gene identification by one-at-a-time models like the random forest is not the most appropriate technique as many genes are co-expressed and functioned cooperatively. An M-value is computed using vsn-transformation [17] and normalization of the data, and a t-statistic is computed using these M-values before being used as inputs for GXNA. To reduce the number of false positives, multiple testing is performed to filter out genes that do not show enough variability against a 0.5 standard deviation for M-values as a threshold [16]. To measure differentially expressed genes, a score called $T\Sigma$ was computed by averaging the t-statistic of each individual gene coming from a set $S = \{g_1, \dots, g_k\}$ of genes where $i = 1, \dots, k$.

As genes can be up-regulated or down-regulated, the absolute values of the t-statistic is taken. The distribution of this scoring function depend on the size of set S. A nonparametric normalization method using the permutations of the phenotypes is used to estimate a null distribution of the score [16]. However, this method is not reliable when the number of phenotypes is small [16]. As an alternative, a parametric assumption is made by normalizing all sets of size k by sampling from random sets of k genes resulting in a function where μ is the mean of $|T|$ over all genes [16]. The assumptions here are that the normalizations only need to depend on the size of S and the individual gene scores are independent (which is unrealistic) [16]. Instead, we normalize by sampling among connected sets of k genes, where μ_k and σ_k are the mean and standard deviation score for randomly

connect sets of k genes, respectively, and σ_k is not needed to be proportional to \sqrt{k} [16]. Scores based on single gene t-statistics ignore the coexpression of genes. Therefore, the sum of expression levels for the genes in S within a microarray is computed before the t-statistics is found. For more information, please refer to [16].

3.3.1 Assessing Significance of Co-expressed Genes with GXNA

With GXNA, interacting/co-expressed genes depending on the target classification were found using permutation-based significance levels. Multiple testing based on the family-wise error rate (FWER) was used when sampling a large sample set to discourage discovering high-scoring clusters with no biological significance [16]. FWER has shown better protective power over false positives in previous research [16]. For an instance, for a dataset with two-phenotype; relapse and no-relapse states, the indices are permuted so that some relapse states are relabeled as no-relapse and vice versa. The analysis is repeated for each permutation and once enough permutations were available, this gives a reliable estimation of the null distribution of the networks scores and allow for the computation of adjusted p-values that control the FWER [16]. According to Nacu et al., the use of $T\Sigma$ scoring function helps to identify groups of genes with p-values very close to the conventional threshold of 5%, reflecting underlying biological significance rather than random chance [16].

3.4 RF-1 vs RF-2

In this study, we focused on two random forest models, a standard random forest model (hereafter referred to as RF-1) and a random forest model based on the GXNA clusters (hereafter referred to as RF-2). In a regular RF model, genes are sorted in increasing order of mean decrease in accuracy or mean decrease in Gini [18] and then used to form biological hypotheses or used for experimental validation [16]. This strategy is limited, as a single gene analysis does not account for co-expression of the genes. For this reason, we developed the second random forest model (RF-2) with the intention of using co-expressed gene clusters identified from GXNA as inputs, following the methods described in the previous paragraph.

3.5 RF++

In addition to the two RF models mentioned above, an RF++ model was considered to identify DE genes. RF++ is a novel generalized random forest-based classifier for cluster-correlated data like genomic data [19]. RF++ identifies important variables in a dataset with large numbers of variables and few subjects using permutation-based proportioning and hence classifies cluster-correlated non-independent data. Subject-level bootstrapping in RF++ assures that approximately 63% of all replicates will end up in the in-bag training set for a particular tree, thus the tree will be unaware of the rest of the independent samples in the dataset (OOB samples) and the error estimate will be unbiased.

3.6 Bayesian Artificial Neural Network (BNN)

The Bayesian Artificial Neural Network (BNN) approach is utilized for modeling the relationship between multiple input variables and output variables. Unlike a regular Multi-Layer Perceptron, BNN incorporates parameter uncertainty in the model through Bayesian inference and regularizes the parameters during the training process [20]. A prior distribution, $p(\omega|\alpha)$, is introduced for the weights and the ANN, where α is the hyperparameter. The evidence procedure is used to find the most probable values of the hyperparameters, α_{MP} , by utilizing the Bayesian regularization technique. The posterior distribution of the network weights is approximated by $p(\omega|\alpha_{MP})$ based on the assumption that the posterior density of hyperparameters, $p(\alpha | D)$, is sharply peaked around α_{MP} . Predictions with BNNs are made by taking the integral over the posterior weight distribution [21].

$$\begin{aligned} p(\omega|D, x, \alpha) &= \int p(\omega|\alpha) \\ &\approx p(\omega|\alpha_{MP}) \int p(\alpha|D) d\alpha \\ &\approx p(\omega|\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

3.6.1 Automatic Relevance Determination (ARD)

In Bayesian modeling, a separate hyperparameter for each input variable, representing the inverse variance of the prior distribution of the weights associated with that input variable (gene), is considered optimal when obtained through the evidence procedure. This results in automatic relevance determination (ARD) prior, where the weights associated with "irrelevant" input variables are set to small values [22]. The optimal α_{MP} is found during the training process and is used to identify the relative importance of the genes.

Two types of networks were trained in this study, with different weight regularization techniques. The first network was a standard neural network and the second network was trained using the Bayesian evidence procedure with ARD prior. Both networks have three hidden nodes and were trained using 10-fold cross validation. To avoid overfitting issues, only hidden nodes ranging from 1 to 10 were considered due to the small sample size. The networks were optimized using forward propagation.

4. Results

The trained models were evaluated using the testing data set in terms of their mean predictive accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC). These are given as mean \pm SD based on the 5 replicated models for each machine learning method. Accuracy is the ratio of correctly predicted disease class of subjects, it is measured on a partitioned testing set. Sensitivity is the ability of our model to correctly identify patients with the disease. Specificity is the ability of our model to correctly identify subjects without the disease. AUC is used as a measurement for model discrimination power.

Table 1: Model Evaluation Summaries of ML Models

	Dataset	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	AUC
RF-1	GSE 2034	0.6739 \pm 0.0012	0.7229 \pm 0.0019	0.2326 \pm 0.0111	0.4372
	GSE 2990	0.5563 \pm 0.0049	0.6333 \pm 0.0090	0.4231 \pm 0.0084	0.5962
RF-2	GSE 2034	0.5767 \pm 0.0017	0.7000 \pm 0.0033	0.2931 \pm 0.0042	0.6954
	GSE 2990	0.6801 \pm 0.0050	0.8109 \pm 0.0071	0.3345 \pm 0.0182	0.7777
RF++	GSE 2034	0.6402 \pm 0.0190	0.4000 \pm 0.0096	0.7206 \pm 0.0087	0.5711
	GSE 2990	0.6176 \pm 0.0322	0.9091 \pm 0.0425	0.0833 \pm 0.0081	0.5378
BNN	GSE 2034	0.6189 \pm 0.0160	0.6357 \pm 0.0054	0.2846 \pm 0.1894	0.5094
	GSE 2990	0.6706 \pm 0.0246	0.7442 \pm 0.0248	0.2846 \pm 0.1894	0.6662
BNN w/ ARD	GSE 2034	0.6296 \pm 0.0120	0.6365 \pm 0.0028	0.4139 \pm 0.0906	0.5478
	GSE 2990	0.5998 \pm 0.0395	0.6591 \pm 0.0248	0.3952 \pm 0.0852	0.6374

4.1 Results of Data Analysis

Table 1 represents the performance evaluations of ML methods for the two breast cancer datasets. RF-2 model had yielded the highest average AUCs (GSE 2034: 0.6954 \pm 0.0004; GSE 2990: 0.7777 \pm 0.0049) among all ML methods with an acceptable discriminative power. It is important to note that, RF-2 has yielded these average AUCs with genes as little as 8 and 25, compared to RF-1 model which had 775 and 1083 genes, for GSE 2034 and GSE 2990, respectively. This is because RF-2 uses a biological driven gene clusters identified through GXNA as its inputs and hence provides more intuitive approach of finding differentially co-expressed genes relevant to breast cancer pathology. The top-ranked genes/clusters that were identified based on the mean decrease in accuracy by RF-1 and RF-2, for the two datasets are given in Figs 1-2 [GSE 2034, RF-1: Fig. 1(top); GSE 2990, RF-1: Fig. 1(bottom); GSE 2034, RF-2: Fig. 2(top); GSE 2990, RF-1: Fig. 2(bottom)]. A higher mean decrease indicates a larger contribution of a certain gene in correctly predicting the status of a breast cancer patient. The darker shade of blue (orange) associated with a gene corresponds to a greater level of up (down)-regulation.

Figure 1: Gene Clusters for RF-1.

Figure 2. Gene Clusters for RF-2.

4.2. Potential DE Genes for Breast Cancer

In this section, we summarize a few genes identified by at least two or more methods discussed in this study. We believe that these genes might be of potential interests for further biological analyses as they have shown some degree of association with the breast cancer pathology.

- **SERPINA3** (Serpine Peptidase Inhibitor, Clade A (Alpha-1 Antitrypsin, Antitrypsin), Member 3) was present and up-regulated in relapsed patients in both RF-1 and RF-2 models. Moreover, this was ranked as one of the top gene by RF++ and BNN. SERPINA3 has been found significant in Malignant Fibrous Histiocytoma, a type of cancer that usually forms in the soft tissue. While SERPINA3 was found to be significant in our analysis, it has not yet been identified to manifest a direct connection to malignant breast cancer. However, we believe it should be further investigated based on the findings of this study.
- **ID1** (Inhibitor Of Differentiation 1) has been identified by four models (RF-1, RF++, and BNN) among the six methods discussed in this study. It has been shown to play an important role in cell differentiation, tumor angiogenesis, cell invasion, and metastasis. Despite the data establishing ID1 as a critical factor for lung metastasis in breast cancer, the pathways and molecular mechanisms of ID1 functions in metastasis remains to be defined until recent studies suggested its role in facilitating tumorous angiogenesis and metastasis.
- **RSBN1** (Round Spermatid Basic Protein 1) has been identified by four models (RF-1, RF++, and BNN) among the six methods used in this study. It has been discovered recently as a potential HIF target, hypoxia-inducible factor, for breast cancer. Hypoxia is a characteristic of breast tumors indicating poor prognosis over time.
- **MAD2L1** (Mitotic Arrest Deficient 2 Like 1) has been identified by two models (RF-1 and RF-2). This is a component of the mitotic spindle assembly checkpoint that prevents the onset of anaphase until all chromosomes are properly aligned at the metaphase plate. The aberrant expression of MAD2L1 has been found to promote tumor formation by inducing chromosomal instability.

We suggest that any identified genes must be verified and further investigated through wet-lab analysis.

5. Discussion

In this study, gene expression analysis on breast cancer pathology were conducted using six methods, five of which are ML based approaches. Although conventional random forest models can be good at predicting (with a higher accuracy) in gene expression analysis, they might not be best at making inferences on specific genes. In contrast to that, GXNA based random forest models took into account the correlation between genetic pathways and was an overall better approach as it utilized prior biological knowledge. In fact, this method had shown some impressive preliminary results in our study. Moreover, we have investigated the use of ARD prior with BNN for possible identification of biomarkers in gene expression analysis. Our findings support the claim that use BNN helps in improving the model discrimination power and hence possibility of diagnosing breast cancer patients with an acceptable accuracy level. Importantly, the ARD prior provides a sophisticated method to evaluate the relative importance of genes associated with the disease pathology. As per our knowledge we are the first to investigate this possibility. We are in the process of applying similar approaches to other disease pathology and will be able to provide a comparison in near future.

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